

1 **Gut barrier breach is sufficient to induce inflammation in the hematopoietic compartment.**

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3 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
4 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
5 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
6 East Islip, NY USA 11730

7 Gut barrier disruption with dextran sodium sulfate resulted in generation of hematopoietic cells with
8 activated inflammatory program gene expression with specific contribution from inflammatory component
9 genes of the lipoxygenase (Alox), cyclooxygenase (Cox) and prostaglandins (PTG) families.

10 The experimental system enabled demonstration of sufficiency of gut barrier disruption for induction of
11 inflammation in cells of the blood.

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The data are pertinent for understanding of how inflammation might arise in an inflammatory bowel
disease, inflammation resulting from deficits in cells of the epithelial barrier but present in
hematopoietic-derived cells of the peripheral blood, including monocytes, providing insight into mechanism
of action in IBD pathogenesis including cell of origin and relative contributions of the epithelial cells of the
GI tract versus blood and immune cells from HSCs: disease activity in intestinal cells as compared to
disease activity in bone marrow-derived cells during instigation of inflammation and during active disease.